

EFFECT OF GRAPHENE AND MWCNTs ON MODE I INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF CFRP

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ABSTRACT

Unidirectional carbon fiber-reinforced composites are widely applied in aeronautical and astronautical structures. However, the weak interlaminar toughness makes composite structures easily being damaged under the low energy impact. Improving composite interlaminar toughness becomes possible as the carbon nanotubes and graphene were discovered. This paper focuses on enhancing the mode I fracture toughness by adding two nano materials of multi-walled carbon nanotubes(MWCNTs) and multi-layers graphene(mG) into interlaminar surface. MWCNTs and mG are sprayed on the central two plies interlaminar surface at the same density 1g/m^2 . Double cantilever beam(DCB) standard test is used to investigate the mode I energy release rate with different toughening strategies. Increasing proportion of the mean fracture toughness are 20.3% (MWCNTs) and 103.2% (mG) respectively. According to SEM analysis, it is revealed that the multi-layers graphene relatively larger superficial area makes the interlaminar fracture toughness increasing remarkably.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite has been widely used for its good properties, such as high strength, high modulus, fatigue resistance, light weight, etc[1,2]. However, composite structures based on carbon fibers cannot avoid disadvantages. For example, the relatively low interlaminar toughness would lead to delamination and other internal damages, when the carbon fiber-reinforced polymer composites (CFRP) suffers low velocity impact loads[3,4]. Although fiber reinforced polymer composites show many advantages compared to other materials, delamination between reinforcing plies remains a major problem limiting further breakthrough. Therefore, improving the fracture properties of unidirectional CFRP has great scientific significance and application value. For this purpose, researchers have made a lot of effort to adding interlaminar materials between plies for toughening the interlaminar.

However, most of them added an interlaminar material with the thickness, which would bring the disadvantages of thickness increasing and in-plane strength decreasing. Kim[5] studied improved interlaminar shear properties of multiscale carbon fiber composites with bucky paper interleaves made from carbon nanofibers. The progress of damage in quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates with interlaminar-toughened layers under tensile fatigue loading has been investigated microscopically. And The material system used was T800H/3900-2 with polyamide-particle- dispersed epoxy layers at every ply

interface[6]. Interleaving laminated composites with electrospun nanofibrous mats comes out as a promising micro-scale strategy to strengthen interlaminar regions of laminated composites[7]. Ductile stainless steel fibres were used as interlayers to enhance the interlaminar fracture toughness of carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRPs)[8]. Till the nano-materials was found, the disadvantages have been gradually overcome.

According to the findings of Iijima[9], carbon nanotubes(CNTs) as an adding material may markedly enhance the fracture toughness of CFRP interlaminar due to its excellent properties. The effect of multi-walled carbon nanotubes(MWCNTs) on the Mode I Interlaminar fracture toughness or the strain energy release rate of woven carbon fiber reinforced composites has been investigated and characterized by double cantilever beam tests. And at the CNT loading of 1.0 g/m^2 , the fracture toughness of sample increases up to 32%[10]. Hierarchical short carbon fibers (SCFs) synthesized with carbon nanotubes (CNTs) were used as CNT-SCF interleaves to increase the mode I delamination fracture energy G_{IC} of carbon fiber/epoxy (CF/EP) composite laminates[11]. The effect of the morphology of the toughening polymer is analyzed by incorporating different polycaprolactone structures in the interlaminar regions[12].

Graphene was found by TKatsnelson[13] and Andre Geim[14]. Graphene is a 2D and a single-layered nanosheet of sp^2 -hybridized carbon atoms, which has been significantly employed for increasing the mechanical and thermal properties of graphene/epoxy composites[15]. The nanomaterial effect on the interfacial properties is an concentrated research point[16]. The hybridization effects of hydrazine reduced graphene oxide (rGO) on the inter-laminar shear strength (ILSS), impact strength, and in-plane fracture toughness of symmetric type carbon fiber/epoxy composite (CF/epoxy) laminates were investigated[17]. A numerical micromechanics study is performed to investigate the effect of using graphene nanoplatelets with theoretical maximum properties and reduced graphene oxide on the mechanical properties and damage mechanism of graphene based nanocomposites[18].

The paper work is to enhance the interlaminar toughness of unidirectional composite laminate. And we focus on the inexpensive toughening strategy. For this purpose, the multi-layers graphene and multiwalled CNTs are chosen. Furthermore, the graphene and MWCNTs will not adding into the epoxy resin, but only spray on the prepreg surface. Hence, two kinds of toughness enhancing strategies are designed: supplying graphene or MWCNTs into the middle interlaminar. And then the specimens are tested under mode I load to determine critical energy release rate[19,20].

2 MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Material

The T700 carbon fibers are fabricated by Toray company. The matrix is thermalsetting epoxy resin. The adding nano-materials are multi-layers graphene and multi-walled carbon nanotubes. MWCNTs are prepared by chemical vapor deposition(CVD). The purity of MWCNTs is greater than 95wt%. The inner diameter is 3-5nm, and the external diameter is 8-15nm. The length of MWCNTs is 3-12 μm . The purity of multi-layers graphene is 95wt%. The thickness is 3.4-8nm. The nanoplate diameter is 5-50 μm . And each graphene nanoplate is composed of 5-10 layers. From the experimental design, three different types of composites laminates are fabricated, which is composed of 30 layers of 0° ply, as shown in Fig.1.

Figure.1. The interlaminar toughening strategies with graphene and MWCNTs

2.2 Composite specimens manufacture

The technological process of DCB composite specimens is shown in Fig.2. The first step is clipping and laying prepregs by the stacking sequence $[0^\circ]_{30}$. The second step is, dispersing the nano materials into the acetone solution under ultrasonic wave for 10 minutes, and spraying the nano materials solution on the surface of middle ply. And the supplements density of $1\text{g}/\text{m}^2$ is chosen to investigate and obtain the interlaminar toughness enhancement. The third step is laying the two parts of 15 plies' prepregs and solidifying them in the autoclave for 3hours at 120°C and 0.4MPa . The last step is cutting the whole plate into dependent specimens, and bonding hinges upon the specimens with epoxy resin. The detailed size of DCB mode I specimen is shown in Fig.3.

Fig.2 Technological process of making mode I specimen

Fig.3 The schematic of DCB mode I specimen

2.3 Set up and equipment

An electro-mechanical universal testing machine with 10KN range is used to conduct the DCB experiment as shown in Fig.4(a). During the test, the force load, displacement and crack length were measured. The specimen fracture surfaces are sprayed with metal to improve the electronic conductivity. And then they are put into the equipment of focused ion beam as shown in Fig.4(b).

Figure.4 (a) Experimental set up; (b) Fracture analysis equipment of focused ion beam

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The mode I fracture toughness are tested for of the specimens with the diverse densities of adding material (Multi-layers graphene and MWCNTs) respectively. In order to eliminate the influence of the measured crack length on the fracture toughness, the crack growth can be calculated by Eq.(1), and the mode I energy release rate G_{IC} is calculated by Eq.(2)[21].

$$a = \sqrt[3]{\frac{3\delta IE_{11}I_z}{2P}} \quad (1)$$

where, δ is the applied displacement, P is the load, E_{11} is the modulus of elasticity of the material,

$$G_{IC} = \frac{P^2}{E_{11}Ib} \left(\frac{3E_{11}I\delta}{2P} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \quad (2)$$

where, G_{IC} is the energy release rate, P is the measured pin load, I is the moment of inertia of one arm, δ is the applied displacement, b is the width of the specimen, E_{11} is the modulus of elasticity of the material.

3.1 DCB fracture toughness test

The load v.s displacement curves of original, MWCNTs and Graphene, are shown in Fig.5(a), (b), (c). Load v.s displacement curves of original specimens appear two stages, which are the linear increasing stage of zero to maximum load and the nonlinear decreasing stage. As the load reaches the maximum load, the load drops abruptly, climbs up and then decreases gradually. However, with regard to the specimens toughed with MWCNTs and graphene, the load v.s displacement curves become linear increasing, nonlinear increasing, and nonlinear decreasing stages. The abrupt load dropping is not

obvious and even disappears. It implies that the nano materials enhance the crack resistance. The bar graphs of different material toughening strategies are shown in Fig.8, the specimens toughened by the graphene and MWCNTs with surface density of 1g/m^2 , shows the remarkable toughness enhancement, compared to the original virgin CFRP. Calculating from the three groups of testing data, the average energy release rate increases from 265.3J/m^2 (Original) to 319.1J/m^2 (MWCNTs) and 539.1J/m^2 (Graphene). Increasing proportion of the mean fracture toughness are 20.3% (MWCNTs) and 103.2% (Graphene) respectively.

Figure.5 Tensile load v.s displacement curve of DCB testing results of specimen : (a) Original (b) MWCNTs (c) Graphene

Figure.6 The G_{IC} of the original, MWCNTs and graphene specimen

3.2 Fracture appearance analysis

The SEM images of multi-layers graphene toughening specimens are shown in Fig.7. As shown in Fig.7, with regard to the multi-layers graphene toughening specimen-01 with $G_{IC}=719.2\text{J/m}^2$: (a) The large amount of non-flush fibers breakage can be seen. (b) Large amount of multi-layers graphene zone are found. (c) For the single multi-layers graphene parallel to the fiber direction, it sticks to fiber surface, and is peeled from the resin matrix by the normal stress. (d) For the vertical multi-layers graphene, it can be found that multi-layers graphene is pulled out from the resin matrix. The horizontal multi-layers graphene surface peeling and the vertical pull out mechanisms explains why the graphene plates enhance the interlaminar toughness remarkably.

Fig.7 SEM images of multi-layers graphene toughening specimen-01 with $G_{IC}=719.2\text{J/m}^2$

4 CONCLUSION

The two supplements strategies were investigated systematically by DCB experiment and SEM image. And the present work concludes that:

(1) The original intention is in consideration of the inexpensive property of multi-layers graphene and MWCNTs. For composite laminates of Mode I fracture, multi-layers graphene can greatly enhance its toughness compared with MWCNTs. The density of graphene and MWCNTs is 1g/m^2 . The surface spraying method is an appropriate nano material adding process.

(2) By adding multi-layers graphene into the interlaminar interface, not only the fracture toughness is improved, but also the load v.s displacement curves become linear increasing, nonlinear increasing, and nonlinear decreasing stages. The abrupt load dropping which occurs in the original virgin specimens, is not obvious and even disappears.

(3) The large amount of non-flush fibers breakage and multi-layers graphene zone can be seen in the specimens of interlaminar toughened with multi-layers graphene. The single multi-layers graphene parallel to the fiber direction is peeled from the resin matrix by the normal stress. The vertical multi-layers graphene, are pulled out from the surrounded resin matrix. The horizontal multi-layers graphene surface peeling and the vertical pull out mechanisms explains why the graphene plates enhance the

interlaminar toughness remarkably.

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